

Business Intelligence and Reporting of Research Data

Final report for the Institutional Underpinnings extension project:

RDM Business Intelligence and Reporting

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Executive summary

Modern research institutions have a growing data problem, and a key step in addressing it is knowing what institutions hold. The Institutional Underpinnings Extension Project: RDM Business Intelligence and Reporting provides a case study on developing an approach to the systematic characterisation and reporting of research data properties to enable strategic decision-making. This project is closely related to the Institutional Underpinnings Extension Project: Retention and Disposal of Research Data, which has focused on the “end-of-life” challenge for research data.¹ The interplay between the two projects is outlined below:

The RDM Business Intelligence and Reporting Project has:

1. Identified some key properties of research data that relate to:
 - a. Cost: Effective management of resources
 - b. Risk: Risks in relation to data exposure / legislative compliance
 - c. Benefit: Evidence of research impact or value
2. Converted these identified properties into a described taxonomy
3. Developed draft definitions for practical, minimal sets of data elements, and trialled the measurement of those properties through the participating institutions
4. Documented common challenges and proposed solutions to institutional adoption of these practices
5. Proposed following recommendations:

Recommendation 1: Digital Research Content Taxonomy

In order to understand the cost, benefit and risk implications of their data holdings, institutions must adapt and embed a common (nationally-agreed) Digital Research Content Taxonomy to evaluate their research data systems and processes and to identify gaps in their ability to gather actionable intelligence about digital research content.

Recommendation 2: Research Data Reporting

- A. Institutions must identify their data custodian(s) and improve their ability to integrate information in support of better decision-making by those custodians

¹ D. Jung et al., ‘Retention and Disposal of Research Data: from current to best practices’, *Zenodo* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076891>

- B. The Australian research sector (Universities, research institutions and peak bodies) must agree on and adopt a minimum research data reporting standard for sector-wide use in alignment with CAUDIT and CAUL annual reporting.

Recommendation 3: Community of practice

A community(-ies) of practice with representatives from key stakeholder groups across the institutions should discuss strategies for sector alignment around best practices in research data characterisation and reporting.

Introduction

Work presented at the eResearch Australasia conference (2022) suggests that over 300Pb of digital research content is held by institutions in the sector for the purpose of future access for reasons such as funding body compliance.² Despite guidelines that require researchers and institutions to manage the retention or disposal of research generated content, such management decisions rarely occur resulting in an accumulation of poorly understood and rapidly growing data holdings, some of which might be valuable, and some of which might be digital research debris. A statement of the problem was captured in the workshops as “the uncontrolled expansion and indefinite retention of uncurated digital content associated with research activities”.

The low institutional practice in assessing these data holdings means extracting and acting on research insights is challenging, limiting the ability to inform strategic research decision-making. The senior stakeholders interviewed who manage these data (e.g. PVCRI/DVCRs, CIOs, eResearch Directors and System Owners) have indicated that they would like more business intelligence and informed benchmarking to enable them to manage their environments and their research data strategies.

On this basis, an ARDC-funded, institutional underpinnings extension project commenced in March 2023 to establish a shared taxonomy and baseline research data reporting format that can be utilised within and across institutions. This report summarises the chronological outputs of the project work packages.

Workshop 1 - community building

A half-day workshop was held on 18 May 2023 in Melbourne, VIC, to *identify key items that would be valuable and feasible to collect about research data*. The workshop was attended by 29 participants, including 7 online participants, from 18 universities and organisations (Table 1). The participants represented various business units, including IT, eResearch services, research strategy, library, and data governance.

Table 1. Participating organisations at Workshop 1.

University		Other Organisation
Charles Darwin University	The University of Adelaide	ARDC
CQUniversity	The University of Melbourne	Astronomy Australia Ltd.
Deakin University	The University of Queensland	CAUDIT
Federation University Australia	The University of Sydney	New Zealand eScience Infrastructure (NeSI)
Macquarie University	The University of Western Australia	
Monash University	University of Technology Sydney	
Swinburne University of Technology	UNSW Sydney	

Identification of Initial BI elements

Prior work by Research Data Culture Conversation (RDCC) was presented at the workshop. The presentation of the RDCC’s initial metrics of potential importance to characterising institutional digital research corpus were used as a reference point for establishing additional metrics of importance to the workshop participants. Work continues to refine these original metrics. The presentation was followed by a group activity in which workshop participants identified

² A. Soo et al., ‘Characterising Australia’s Experience with Research Data at Scale’. *Monash University* [Presentation], 02 Nov. 2022. <https://doi.org/10.26180/21454719.v1>

potential BI elements of importance about research data for regular collection (Table 2). It is acknowledged that the workshop captures the priority/of interest elements reflective of the business areas represented by participants present in the workshop, which were not captured. A different representation from across university stakeholders may produce a different set of elements.

Table 2. Identified BI elements categorised by purpose

Demonstration of:	Corresponding elements
Cost: Effective management of resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volume (Research Data) • Volume by owner/custodian • Volume by FoR code • Volume by location • Cost • Volume by RAiD • Number of research projects • Volume by retention period
Risk: Risk profile and mitigation requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HREC data • Volume of Sensitive Data • Volume of First Nations Data
Benefit: Research Impact / Value (including Access / Reuse capability)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Volume of data (by access restriction categories) • Volume of re-used data • Reporting on discipline/community repositories • Velocity from the start of a project to DOI • Dataset publications • Downloads by IP Addresses • Number of Citations

Assessing measurement feasibility

The partner institutions were invited to complete a post-workshop task to describe their current institutional capabilities in collecting the identified BI elements. Note: The current capability scan represents the best efforts by the representatives from each institution and is not definitive. Their combined responses are shown in Table 3.

The task did not define “accessible with effort”. Feedback from participants suggested that while an “accessible with effort” response indicated that data was available, the extent of efforts such as manual or automated, reproducibility, and sustainability were not easily summarised.

All participants indicated platform-to-platform variability in extractable data. For example, volume data from a dedicated research data management system (that is provisioned after RDMP is completed) is accessible, but research content volume from self-provisioned, mixed-used institutional systems (e.g., OneDrive) or unlicensed systems is not identifiable. While the partner institutions could access the data on the number of HREC approvals, little success is reported in linking the HREC approval and data sensitivity classification to research data volume. Reporting on the volume and number of datasets in institutional repositories is a mature process across the three partner institutions, but more variability was observed in accessing relevant data from external repositories.

Table 3. Current institutional capabilities at partner institutions.

Business Intelligence: Effective management of resources			
	UNSW	USyd	UTS
Key Report: Volume			
Total research content (data and associated)	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort
by owner/custodian	Readily Accessible	Readily Accessible	Accessible with effort
by service/location	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Readily Accessible	Readily Accessible
by FoR code	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort
by RAiD	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
by grant	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
by retention period	Accessible with effort	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Accessible with effort
Total Research data	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort	No response
Key Report: Cost			
Total	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Accessible with effort	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
by infrastructure/service	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Readily Accessible	Accessible with effort
by environmental impact	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
by decision points (e.g., curation, training)	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
by FoR code	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort
Key Report: Research Project			
Total number	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort

per CI	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort
per FoR Code	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort	No response
Business Intelligence: Risk Management			
	UNSW	USyd	UTS
Key Report: HREC Data			
Total number of approvals	Readily Accessible	Readily Accessible	Accessible with effort
by CI	Readily Accessible	Readily Accessible	Accessible with effort
by FoR code	No response	Accessible with effort	No response
Volume per HREC approval	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Accessible with effort
by service/location	Accessible with effort	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
Key Report: Sensitive / Protected Data			
Total volume of Sensitive Data	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Accessible with effort
by ethics approval	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
Total volume of First Nations Data	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Accessible with effort
by ethics approval	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
Business Intelligence: Access / Reuse capability			
	UNSW	USyd	UTS
Key Report: Volume			
Total in institutional repository	Readily Accessible	Readily Accessible	Accessible with effort
by access restriction category (mediated, open)	Readily Accessible	Accessible with effort	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
Total in external repositories	Readily Accessible	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Accessible with effort
by access restriction category (mediated, open)	Accessible with effort	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
Business Intelligence: Research Impact / Value			
	UNSW	USyd	UTS
Key Report: Dataset Publications			
Total number of published datasets	Readily Accessible	Accessible with effort	Readily Accessible
by FoR code	Readily Accessible	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort
correlated to research cost	Accessible with effort	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
Total number of citations	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort
by FoR code	Accessible with effort	Accessible with effort	Inaccessible / doesn't exist
correlated to research cost	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist	Inaccessible / doesn't exist

Workshop 2 - continuing the conversation

The second workshop was held on 24 August 2023 in Sydney, NSW, to discuss and establish a set of agreed taxonomy and common reporting schema. The workshop was attended by 33 participants, including 14 online participants, from 17 universities and organisations (Table 4). The participants represented various business units, including IT, eResearch services, research strategy, library, and data governance.

Table 4. Participating organisations at Workshop 2.

University		Other Organisation
Macquarie University	The University of Western Australia	ARDC
Monash University	University of Southern Queensland	CAUL
The University of Adelaide	University of Tasmania	CSIRO
The University of Melbourne	University of Technology Sydney	Microscopy Australia
The University of Queensland	UNSW Sydney	NeSI
The University of Sydney	Western Sydney University	

Digital Research Content Taxonomy

Participants of the first workshop identified potential BI elements of importance about research data for regular collection (Table 3). These potential BI elements revealed important properties of digital research content and formed a basis for a draft taxonomy (Figure 1), aligned to the business drivers previously identified (Benefits, Cost, Risk). Table 5 has been developed post workshop 2 to support clarity on the taxonomy categories.

Figure 1. Proposed Digital Research Content Taxonomy

Table 5. Digital Research Content Taxonomy Description

Method of categorisation	Category	Description
<p>Data publishing</p> <p>Publication status and accessibility to the broader research community</p> <p>This categorisation aims to provide actionable intelligence on the institutional capability in benefits and cost management.</p>	Open	Refers to the availability of research outputs via the internet, such that any user can find, freely access, read, share and reuse the research output. Sharing and reuse is facilitated through open licensing. ³
	Embargoed	Data that is under embargo for a defined period of time, after which, it becomes openly accessible. Metadata record is published for discoverability.
	Mediated	Data that is shared with others only with conditional approval. Metadata record is published for discoverability.
	Closed	Data that is not made available to others. Metadata record may be published for discoverability.
	Unpublished	Unpublished data accessible to authorised users only.
<p>Discipline</p> <p>Classifying data based on branches of knowledge or fields of study that are researched</p> <p>This categorisation aims to provide actionable intelligence on the institutional capability in benefits management</p>	FoR	Method of categorisation based on field of research (FoR) code ⁴ of the research projects generating or acquiring the data
	Org Unit	Method of categorisation of research data based on the organisational unit of the chief investigator of the research project generating or acquiring the research data
<p>Ethics</p> <p>Classifying data based on ethical considerations and principles that govern how the data was collected, used, and managed during the research process</p> <p>This categorisation aims to provide actionable intelligence on the institutional capability in risk management.</p>	Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research	All research that impacts or is of particular significance to Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples, including the planning, collection, analysis and dissemination of information or knowledge, in any format or medium, which is about or may affect Indigenous peoples, either collectively or individually. ⁵
	Human Research	<p>Human research is conducted with or about people, or their data or tissue. Human participation in research is therefore to be understood broadly, to include the involvement of human beings through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● taking part in surveys, interviews or focus groups; ● undergoing psychological, physiological or medical testing or treatment; ● being observed by researchers; ● researchers having access to their personal documents or other materials; ● the collection and use of their body organs, tissues or fluids (eg skin, blood, urine, saliva, hair, bones, tumour and other biopsy specimens) or their exhaled breath; ● access to their information (in individually identifiable, re-identifiable or non-identifiable form) as part of an existing published or unpublished source or database.⁶
	Animal Research	Data collected or acquired in the conduct of research that uses animals for scientific purposes ⁷
	No ethics approval	Data collected or acquired in the conduct of research that has no extra ethical implications and does not require ethical approval

³ National Health and Medical Research Council, 'NHMRC Open Access Policy', *NHMRC* (Canberra, 2022), 5, <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/resources/nhmrc-open-access-policy>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

⁴ Australian Bureau of Statistics. "Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC)." *ABS* (Canberra, 2020), <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/classifications/australian-and-new-zealand-standard-research-classification-anzsrc/latest-release>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

⁵ Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies, 'AIATSIS code of ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander research', *AIATSIS* (Canberra 2020), 2, <https://aiatsis.gov.au/sites/default/files/2022-02/aiatsis-code-ethics-jan22.pdf>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

⁶ National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council and Universities Australia, 'National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research', *NHMRC* (Canberra, 2023), 7, <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/publications/national-statement-ethical-conduct-human-research-2023>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

⁷ National Health and Medical Research Council, 'Australian code for the care and use of animals for scientific purposes', *NHMRC* (Canberra, 2013), <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/publications/australian-code-care-and-use-animals-scientific-purposes>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

Frequency of use Classifying data based on how often it is accessed and utilised This categorisation aims to provide actionable intelligence on the institutional capability in benefits and cost management.	Active	Data currently in use
	Inactive	Data that is no longer actively used
Function / Value⁸ Classifying data based on the value and function. This method of categorisation distinguishes Research Data that is valuable and serves the function of “validating research findings and/or enable reproduction of research” vs. Research Debris, which does not. This categorisation aims to provide actionable intelligence on the institutional capability in benefits and cost management.	Research Data	<p>Research Data are the primary and valuable information collected or generated during a research study. These data are typically gathered through systematic methods and processes, such as experiments, surveys, observations, or simulations, to answer research questions or test hypotheses. Research data can take various forms, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative data: Numerical measurements, counts, or statistical information. Qualitative data: Descriptive, non-numerical information, often in the form of text, images, or videos. Raw data: Unprocessed data directly collected from observations or experiments. Processed data: Data that have been cleaned, organised, and analysed to derive meaningful insights. <p>Research data are essential for supporting the conclusions and findings of a research project. Researchers should document and manage their data carefully to ensure its integrity, reproducibility, and future usability.</p>
	Research Debris	<p>Research debris, sometimes referred to as "research waste," refers to the byproducts or less valuable components of the research process that may not contribute directly to the research objectives or outcomes. This term encompasses various elements, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unusable data: Data that are incomplete, inaccurate, or irrelevant to the research question and cannot be used for analysis. Failed experiments: Experiments that did not yield meaningful results or were not conducted correctly. Unpublished findings: Research findings that are not reported in publications or shared with the scientific community. <p>Research debris can result from various factors, including trial and error, changes in research direction, or unsuccessful attempts to answer research questions. While research debris may not directly contribute to the main research objectives, it can still offer insights or lessons learned that may be valuable for the research process.</p>
Funding source Classifying data based on the financial support or sponsorship that enabled the research project's data collection, analysis, or creation This categorisation aims to provide actionable intelligence on the institutional capability in benefits management	Publicly funded research	Data collected or acquired in the conduct of research that receives financial support from government agencies
	Privately funded research	Data collected or acquired in the conduct of research that receives financial support from private entities
	Other	Data collected or acquired in the conduct of research that receives financial support from other sources
Ownership Ownership can be defined as the act of having legal rights and complete control over one or more data elements. Ownership defines and provides information about the rightful owner of data assets and the acquisition, use and distribution	Internal	Data that is owned by the institution or institutional staff
	External	Data that is owned by an external entity but held at the institution (e.g., research data generated by research involving Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples and communities)

⁸ Descriptions for these categories generated using ChatGPT using the prompt “What is the difference between research data and research debris?”

<p>policy implemented by the data owner.⁹</p> <p>This categorisation aims to provide actionable intelligence on the institutional capability in risk management.</p>	Higher Degree by Research	Data generated as part of a Higher Degree by Research (HDR) project as defined by Australian Qualifications Framework ¹⁰
	Coursework	Data generated in conduct of a research project as part of a coursework degree
<p>Privacy</p> <p>Classifying data based on the level of personal or sensitive information it contains and the corresponding privacy considerations</p> <p>This categorisation aims to provide actionable intelligence on the institutional capability in risk management.</p>		<p>Information or an opinion about an identified individual, or an individual who is reasonably identifiable:</p> <p>(a) whether the information or opinion is true or not; and</p> <p>(b) whether the information or opinion is recorded in a material form or not¹¹</p> <p>This category of data includes Sensitive information subset, which is defined as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● information or an opinion (that is also personal information) about an individual's: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ racial or ethnic origin ○ political opinions ○ membership of a political association ○ religious beliefs or affiliations ○ philosophical beliefs ○ membership of a professional or trade association ○ membership of a trade union ○ sexual orientation or practices, or ○ criminal record ● health information about an individual ● genetic information (that is not otherwise health information) ● biometric information that is to be used for the purpose of automated biometric verification or biometric identification, or ● biometric templates¹²
	Personal Information	
	Not personal Information	Data that is not personal information
<p>Sentencing</p> <p>Sentencing is the process of matching the agency's digital research content to a relevant records authority to establish its value and for how long it must be kept.¹³ It should be noted that data can move between sentencing categories. For example, some data could be classified as "Within minimum retention period" upon creation, but once the retention period is past, and not extended, it would be more appropriately reclassified as "No Retention Period"</p> <p>This categorisation aims to provide actionable intelligence on the institutional capability in cost and risk management.</p>	Permanent	Data that must be retained indefinitely. Reasons for this include, but not limited to, being required as State archives or permanent records according to the state retention and disposal authorities.
	Within Maximum Retention Period	Data that must be disposed of at the end of a prescribed retention period according to the data usage agreements or licences. For example, an external dataset received can have a maximum retention period specified in a data sharing agreement.
	Within Minimum Retention Period	Data that must be retained for the minimum retention period as specified in state retention and disposal authorities
	No Retention Period	Data that can be retained or disposed of under the institutional normal administrative practices guidelines or data past the minimum retention period specified in state retention and disposal authorities

⁹ R. Hanisch et al., 'NIST Research Data Framework (RDaF): Version 1.5', *National Institute of Standards and Technology* (Gaithersburg, 2023), 31, <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.1500-18r1>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

¹⁰ Tertiary Education Quality and Standards Agency, 'Australian Qualifications Framework', *TEQSA* (Melbourne, 2023), <https://www.teqsa.gov.au/how-we-regulate/acts-and-standards/australian-qualifications-framework>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

¹¹ Office of the Australian Information Commissioner, 'Australian Privacy Principles guidelines', *OAIC* (Sydney, 2022), Chapter B Key Concepts, <https://www.oaic.gov.au/privacy/australian-privacy-principles/australian-privacy-principles-guidelines>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ National Archives of Australia, 'Appraisal and sentencing', *NAA* (ACT, 2023), <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/disposing-information/appraisal-and-sentencing>, accessed 31 Oct. 2023.

Digital research content reporting schema

After the first workshop, the partner institutions had reported their current capabilities in collecting the identified data elements (Table 3). In the second workshop, participants refined the definitions of the minimum data elements, and partner organisations were invited to complete a post-workshop task to report their current data for these data elements to test the draft data element definitions. Their combined responses are shown in Table 6. While preliminary, the data show key differences between organisations. For example, for the number of projects, UNSW reported all grant records, Higher Degree by Research projects and manually created RDMPs whereas UTS only reported the active RDMPs. This activity also showed that none of the institutions were able to report on the total volume of research data as it is currently defined, indicating a need to either re-evaluate its inclusion in the report or modify its definition.

Table 6. Minimum data element definitions

Data Element	Technical Definition	Data (2023)
Total volume of research content	<i>The total volume of research content held in any format in institutionally managed systems. Include the volume of all files in the systems for the relevant year, not just those added during that year. Include the volume of research content in mixed-use systems (e.g., OneDrive) if research content can be identified. Exclude strategies for resilience.</i> <i>Report in units of Terabytes.</i>	UNSW: 14,736 USyd: 13,800 UTS: 2,990
Total volume of research data	<i>This is the total volume of research data in any format that are categorised as research data (by your institution) in institutionally managed systems for a minimum period as defined by legislation. Include the volume of all files in the systems for the relevant year, not just those added during that year. Exclude the volume of research data in non-institutionally-managed infrastructure.</i> <i>Report in units of Terabytes.</i>	UNSW: Not reported USyd: Not reported UTS: Not reported
Number of research projects	<i>The unique count of research activities, which are currently active and recognised within University's research office services.</i>	UNSW: 72,339 USyd: Not reported UTS: 1,102
Total number of HREC approvals	<i>This is the total number of active research proposals approved by Human Research Ethics Committee in the relevant year where the chief investigator is an internal institutional researcher. Include all active approvals for the relevant year, not just those added during that year. Include records where research proposals by an internal researcher are approved by an external HREC.</i>	UNSW: 3,299 USyd: Not reported UTS: 2,181
Total number of published datasets	<i>This is the total number of published research dataset records held in the institutionally managed repository(ies). Include metadata-only records of published research datasets where the output itself is not in the repository. Include all published research datasets in the repository for the relevant year, not just those added during that year.</i>	UNSW: 593 USyd: Not reported UTS: 279
Total volume of published datasets in institutional repository	<i>This is the total volume of published research datasets held in the institutionally managed repository(ies). Include all published research datasets in the repository for the relevant year, not just those added during that year.</i> <i>Report in units of Terabytes.</i>	UNSW: 1.4 USyd: 0.01 UTS: 5

Workshop 3 - broader consultation

The third and final workshop was held on 16 October 2023 in Brisbane, Queensland, at the eResearch Australasia conference 2023, *to validate the project outputs with the sector and discuss pathways to institutional adoption*. The workshop was attended by 53 participants, from 24 universities and organisations (Table 7). The participants represented various business units, including IT, eResearch services, research strategy, library, and data governance. The project outputs were presented once again at a Birds of a Feather (BoF) session at the same conference on 19 October 2023. Note: as there was a significant crossover between the current project with the other IU Extension Project, Retention and Disposal of Research Data, the workshop and BoF session were jointly held for both projects. Therefore, some of the content in this section is identical to that in the Retention and Disposal of Research Data final report.¹⁴

Table 7. Participating organisations at Workshop 3.

University	Other Organisation
Australian National University	University of Canberra ARDC
Curtin University	University of Otago Council of Australian University Librarians (CAUL)
La Trobe University	University of Technology Sydney CSIRO
Monash University	UNSW Sydney Manaaki Whenua Landcare Research
The University of Adelaide	Western Sydney University Microscopy Australia
The University of Melbourne	National Institute of Informatics
The University of Queensland	NeSI
The University of Sydney	Netapp
University of Auckland	Sax Institute

¹⁴ D. Jung et al., 'Retention and Disposal of Research Data: from current to best practices', *Zenodo* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076891>

Evaluating project outputs

The participants were presented with the Digital Research Content Taxonomy (Figure 1) and asked to score (1-10) each category on 1) the institutional impact if it is characterised and 2) the feasibility of characterisation and measurement (Figure 2). All categories received an averaged score greater than 5 on impact, but a more varying score on feasibility.

Figure 2. Validating the research data taxonomy (n=50). Aggregation (A) and individual responses (B) shown.

The participants were also asked to rate the usefulness of project outputs. The same question was asked to the participants of the BoF session, of which results are shown in Figure 3. There was overwhelming support for the project outputs.

Figure 3. Participant responses to the usefulness of project outputs for their institution. Results from Workshop 3 (A; n=45) and Birds of a feather session (B; n=72) shown.

Institutional adoption challenges and proposed solutions

In Workshop 3, participants discussed common institutional adoption challenges and solutions for the four common stakeholder groups: Researchers, Division of Research, Library and IT (Table 8). It should be noted that while some stakeholder-specific challenges were identified, there were common themes for all stakeholder groups. Key lessons from this exercise were:

1. Roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders should be more clearly defined
2. Motivation for researchers needs to be formulated
3. Systems should enable and simplify policy and procedures
4. Automation is essential to scalability
5. Research discipline-specific considerations must be made
6. Sector-wide, and cross-unit alignment is essential for advocacy, both internal and external

Table 8. Institutional adoption challenges and proposed solutions

Stakeholder	Challenges	Proposed Solutions	Engagement strategy (elevator pitch)
Researchers	Lack of incentive	Advocacy for carrots and sticks (e.g. funder)	Business Driver <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Quality of Research Output ● Reputation Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research domain-specific considerations ● Effective IT support
	Time and resource constraints	System integration to remove redundancies	Methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Effective engagement with diverse stakeholders including Faculty, Research Office, CDO and others Assumptions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● There is a risk of inaction ● Benefit & cost can be quantified
	Lack of support	Self-service resources, support personnel	Goals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Capture new projects going forward ● Review past projects ● Iterative improvement
Division of Research	Resource constraints	Machine actionable DMP	Business Driver <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Risk reduction ● Cost estimation ● Response to emerging policies Resources <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RACI ● Benchmarking from the sector
	Unclear responsibilities	Cross-unit, shared vision, clear articulation of responsibilities	Methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cross-unit engagement ● Contextualise the need Assumptions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competition for resources ● Data is growing
	Alignment of priorities	Clear articulation of benefits (risk, compliance, impact), national advocacy	Goals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Incorporated into key performance indicators ● Recognition in risk register

Library	Unclear responsibilities	Cross-unit, shared vision, clear articulation of responsibilities	<p>Business Driver</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Demonstration of Libray’s value in research data management capabilities <p>Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cross-functional team ● Benchmarking from the sector <p>Methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identify champions ● Leverage existing cross-unit groups <p>Assumptions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Research data management is a library priority ● There is resource to undertake the work <p>Goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data-driven decision making ● Engagement that results in culture change
	Lack of support for broader culture change	Budget for engagement activities, use CAUL, national alignment	
	Low motivation	Funder advocacy	
IT	Unclear responsibility	Creation of and support for research focused IT, specialised data managers	<p>Business Driver</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cost & Risk minimisation ● Reputation protection <p>Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Current-state analysis ● Cost-benefit analysis ● Buy-in from stakeholders <p>Methods</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cross-unit engagement <p>Assumptions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data is growing ● Legislation is getting more difficult to comply with <p>Goals</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Automation ● Scalable solution
	Unclear requirements	Co-develop policy and processes, RACI matrix	
	Lack of resources	Clear business case to the executives	
	Fragmentation of data / metadata	Defined data models	

Establishing a community of practice

At the BoF session, there was significant interest in participating in a community of practice (CoP) if established, to sustain and further develop project outputs (Figure 4). The interested participants were asked to complete a form to note down their contact details (n=44). Their affiliations are shown in Table 9.

Figure 4. Participant responses to the interest in participating in a CoP to sustain and further develop project outputs (n=75).

Table 9. Affiliation of the participants who showed interest in participating in the CoP.

University	Other Organisation
CQUniversity	University of Technology Sydney AgResearch
Flinder University	University of the Sunshine Coast ARDC
La Trobe University	UNSW Sydney BioGrid Australia
Monash University	Western Sydney University CSIRO
Queensland University of Technology	Department of Defence
The University of Melbourne	Microscopy Australia
The University of Queensland	National Institute of Informatics
The University of Sydney	NeSI
University of Auckland	Netapp
University of Southern Queensland	Walter and Eliza Hall Institute of Medical Research

Challenges and recommendations

The project has highlighted key challenges and recommendations in improving business intelligence reporting capabilities for internal and national use.

Challenge 1: We can report about the systems holding the data but have a limited ability to report about the data itself.

This matters because actionable intelligence needs reporting on the properties of the data. But what do we need to know? Through a series of significant subject matter expert consultations, this project produced a Digital Research Content Taxonomy that highlights important properties about data that inform decision-making.

Recommendation 1: Digital Research Content Taxonomy

In order to understand the cost, benefit and risk implications of their data holdings, institutions must adapt and embed a common (nationally-agreed) Digital Research Content Taxonomy to evaluate their research data systems and processes and to identify gaps in their ability to gather actionable intelligence about digital research content.

Challenge 2: Reporting around research data is often not centralised.

For example, information around DMP uptake, infrastructure usage, usage across faculties, data sensitivity, links to funding, ethics applications, etc. is not readily available to any single department. Collating these stats requires considerable time and resource investment or never occurs, meaning institutions do not have a bird's eye view of their research data and associated services and platforms and cannot address needs holistically. When such integration does occur, there are often gaps and deficits in the available data, impacting the ability to make effective decisions, or there is extraneous data that does not have functional value in reporting.

The existing sector-wide reporting landscape reflects this segregation. Council of Australasian University Directors of Information Technology (CAUDIT) produces an annual benchmarking report on ICT-related activities within each member institution, including total ICT investment.¹⁵ Council of Australian University Librarians (CAUL) also performs regular data collection on “collections, staffing, expenditure, library services, and library clients for all Australian and New Zealand university libraries”.¹⁶ National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) requires Human Research Ethics Committees (HRECs) to self-report on their activities annually, including the total number of approvals.¹⁷ Currently, however, there are few research data-specific elements in these reports. Further, different departments participate in the data collection and extract insights from each of these reports, therefore their requirements and motivation need to be well considered to drive buy-in for research data reporting that cuts across different domains.

The partner institutions have reported that the contribution to the minimal research data report not only was beneficial for benchmarking purposes, but to identify the informational silos that existed within their own institutions.

Recommendation 2: Research Data Reporting

- A. Institutions must identify their data custodian(s) and improve their ability to integrate information in support of better decision-making by those custodians

¹⁵ <https://caudit.edu.au/resources/2023-scope-of-it-and-definition-of-data-elements-caudit-benchmarking-system-v1-0/> (member login required)

¹⁶ <https://www.caul.edu.au/programs-projects/statistics-services>

¹⁷ <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/research-policy/ethics/human-research-ethics-committees>

- B. The Australian research sector (Universities, research institutions and peak bodies) must agree on and adopt a minimum research data reporting standard for sector-wide use in alignment with CAUDIT and CAUL annual reporting.

Challenge 3: When we talk about research data, we talk about two different things.

As summarised in the Appendix, *government funding agencies in the US and Canada adopt a functional definition of research data: data that serve the function of validating or allowing the replication of research findings.* The implication is that there is research content, termed research debris for the purpose of this report, that does not serve this function (such as duplicate copies of data or data resulting from the use of incorrectly calibrated instruments) and therefore is not research data. Distinguishing the two categories of digital research content can provide a strategic framework for decision-making: managing research data would be different in business drivers, priority, and approach from managing research debris.

By contrast, in Australia, NHMRC definition of data encapsulates the total corpus: “Data can refer to raw data, cleaned data, transformed data, summary data and metadata (data about data). It can also refer to research outputs and outcomes.” (refer to the Appendix for full definition). On the level of organisational policies, however, not all Australian Universities and research organisations adopt this broader view, but follow the functional, narrower definition like the US and Canada (Sppl. Table 1). Therefore, reporting on and discussing research data is challenging.

The project has identified these challenges through a series of sector engagement activities. In Workshop 3, the participants were asked to score these challenges twice on a scale of 1 to 10. There was a strong agreement with the challenges documented (Figure 5A). While there were largely balanced responses, challenge 3 specifically had a skew towards requiring sector alignment (Figure 5B). This is consistent with the suggestion of using sector alignment as a business case resource for institutional adoption (Table 7), and evidence of great community interest in sustaining the sector alignment efforts through a community of practice (Figure 4).

Figure 5. Participant agreement with the challenges (A) and whether these challenges are dependent on individual institutional processes or sector alignment (B)

Recommendation 3: Community of practice

A community(-ies) of practice with representatives from key stakeholder groups across the institutions should discuss strategies for sector alignment around best practices in research data characterisation and reporting.

Conclusion

Modern research institutions have a growing data problem, and the first step in addressing it is knowing what we have. The Institutional Underpinnings extension project: RDM Business Intelligence and Reporting provides a case study on developing an approach to the systematic characterisation and reporting of research data properties to enable strategic decision-making. Finally, the project produced three recommendations related to the institutional adoption of the project outputs, importantly the need to continue the efforts for sector alignment through a community of practice. The successful project outputs and the significant sector interest provide evidence for the validity of such an approach.

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Appendix – defining “Research Data”

Various attempts at defining research data are summarised below.

a. US – National Institute of Health

The National Institute of Health (NIH) defines *Scientific Data* in the [Final NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing](#) (2023), NOT-OD-21-013, as

the recorded factual material commonly accepted in the scientific community as of sufficient quality to validate and replicate research findings, regardless of whether the data are used to support scholarly publications. Scientific data do not include laboratory notebooks, preliminary analyses, completed case report forms, drafts of scientific papers, plans for future research, peer reviews, communications with colleagues, or physical objects, such as laboratory specimens

b. Canada – Tri-agency Data Management Policy

Canada’s three federal granting agencies, the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR), the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (NSERC), and the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC) created [Tri-agency Data Management Policy](#), in which research data is defined as

... data that are used as primary sources to support technical or scientific enquiry, research, scholarship, or creative practice, and that are used as evidence in the research process and/or are commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings and results. Research data may be experimental data, observational data, operational data, third party data, public sector data, monitoring data, processed data, or repurposed data. What is considered relevant research data is often highly contextual, and determining what counts as such should be guided by disciplinary norms.

c. Australia – National Health and Medical Research Council

Australia’s key governmental funding body, National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC) defines data in its [Open Access Policy](#) (similar to the definition in National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research 2023):

The terms ‘data’ and ‘information’ are often used interchangeably. Data can refer to raw data, cleaned data, transformed data, summary data and metadata (data about data). It can also refer to research outputs and outcomes. Likewise, information takes many different forms. ‘Data’ is usually used to refer to bits of information in their raw form, whereas ‘information’ generally refers to data that have been interpreted, analysed or contextualised.

Data and information may include but not be limited to:

- *what people say in interviews, focus groups, questionnaires/surveys, personal histories and biographies*
- *images, audio recordings and other audio-visual materials*
- *records generated for administrative purposes (e.g. billing, service provision) or as required by legislation (e.g. disease notification)*
- *digital information generated directly by the population through their use of mobile devices and the internet*
- *physical specimens or artefacts*
- *information generated by analysis of existing personal information (from clinical, organisational, social, observational or other sources)*

- *observations*
- *results from experimental testing and investigations*
- *information derived from human biospecimens such as blood, bone, muscle and urine.*

d. Australia – Institutional research data management policy

Australian institutions define research data in their own research data management policies and guidelines, implemented to satisfy the requirements of the NHMRC Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research. Most institutional policies and guidelines distinguish primary/research materials from research data, where materials are objects acquired during a scholarly investigation from which research data can be derived. Further, most definitions recognise that the materials and research data can be both physical and digital.

Supplementary Table 1. Research data definitions from Australian Universities and other research organisations. Some Australian Universities were excluded from this list as no definition of research data or similar were publicly available. Note: This table represents the best efforts of the project team at the time and is intended only as a guide to various definitions of research data in Australian institutions. The information presented here is not definitive or exhaustive, and readers must satisfy themselves of the currency of the information presented here.

State/Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
ACT	Australian National University	Primary Materials refer to physical or virtual objects acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which research data may be derived including but not limited to photographs, sound recordings, questionnaire responses, and biological samples.	Research Data includes all data created and/or generated by researchers in the course of their research work, on which an argument, theory, test or hypothesis, or another research output is based, for which the University has a custodial responsibility under relevant agreements and the relevant archives/record keeping acts.		Procedure: Research data management
ACT	University of Canberra	Objects (original physical, creative, visual or electronic) acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which Research Data may be derived.	Any data collected for the purposes of research, including associated primary materials (laboratory books, samples, video, photographs, creative works) and associated information required to understand or interpret the data, and any information pertaining to approvals for collection of the data or samples from which the data were obtained.	Information: Any information that accompanies the research data and primary materials, including that which is necessary for the comprehension or interpretation of those data or materials (commonly referred to as metadata – see below).	Management of Research Data, Primary Materials and Information Policy
ACT	CSIRO		Data obtained to inform research. Data may be in the form of facts, observations, images, computer program results, recordings, measurements or experience; they may be numerical, descriptive, visual or tactile. Data may be raw, cleaned or processed; generated, acquired, or collated for the work and may be held in any format or media.		O&A Data Management Procedure
NSW	Australian Catholic University	Research Data Materials: Physical objects collected and/or used during research from which Research Data may be obtained such as biological samples, survey questionnaires, measurements, recordings, texts and computer results.	Data generated throughout and beyond the research life-cycle. Data that are in the form of facts, observations, images, computer program results, recordings, measurements, narratives or experiences on which an argument, theory, test, hypothesis or another research output is based. Data may be numerical, descriptive, visual or tactile. Data may be raw, or analysed, experimental or observational and may be held in any format or media. Data include records that are necessary for the reconstruction and evaluation of reported results of research and the events and processes leading to those results.		Research Data Management Policy
NSW	Charles Sturt University		Research data relates to data collected, generated or used in research. This includes but is not limited to data in the form of facts, observations, images, computer program results, surveys, recordings, measurements or experiences on which an argument, theory, test or hypothesis, or another research output is based. Data may be numerical, textual, descriptive, visual or tactile and includes artifacts. It may be		Research Data Management Policy

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
			raw, learned or processed, and may be held in any format or media. Research data is collected or created, not authored.		
NSW	Macquarie University	Research Materials are defined as primary materials which are physical objects such as biological samples, mineral samples, survey questionnaires, measurements, recordings, texts and computer notes, from which research data may be derived.	Data means research data, which includes primary materials or information held in any digital format or media, or anything that can be digitised, on which an argument, theory, test or hypothesis, or another research output is based. Data may also include other 'digital research objects' such as analytical code that support research outcomes. Research data may be in the form of facts, observations, images, computer program results, recordings, questionnaires/surveys, biographies, audio files, physical specimens or artefacts, measurements, experiences or various other forms. Data may be numerical, descriptive, visual or tactile and could be raw, cleaned or analysed. Data referred to in this Policy does not include the information about research performance or statistical research data which is used by Macquarie University for planning and budget purposes or that which is reported to government agencies, for example, Excellence in Research for Australia.		Research Data Management Policy
NSW	Southern Cross University	Primary Materials means physical or virtual items that are collected or generated through the research from which Research Data can be developed, such as biological samples, questionnaires and recordings.	Research Data - means data as facts, observations, computer results, measurements or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Research Data may be numerical, descriptive or visual. Research Data may be durable records derived from Primary Materials such as assays, test results, transcripts, and laboratory and field notes. Research Data may be raw or analysed, experimental or observational. Research Data includes information necessary for the reconstruction and evaluation of results of research.		Research Data Management Policy
NSW	University of New England	Research Materials are defined as primary materials which are physical objects such as biological samples, mineral samples, survey questionnaires, measurements, recordings, texts and computer notes, from which research data may be derived.	Research data means data as facts, observations, computer results, measurements or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Data may be numerical, descriptive or visual. Data may be raw or analysed, experimental or observational. Data include records that are necessary for the reconstruction and evaluation of reported results of research and the events and processes leading to those results, regardless of the form or the media on which they may be recorded.		Management and Storage of Research Data and Materials Policy

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
NSW	University of New South Wales			<p>Institutional Data: The representation of facts, concepts or instructions in a formalised (consistent and agreed) manner suitable for communication, interpretation or processing by human or automatic means. Typically comprised of numbers, words or images. The format and presentation of data may vary with the context in which they are used. Data are not Information until used in a particular context for a particular purpose. (Office of the Australian Information Commissioner (OAIC), 2013)</p> <p>Data are typically considered to be conceptually at the lowest level of abstraction. In the context of this Policy this term includes all institutional data including research, administrative, and learning and teaching artefacts.</p> <p>Research data and materials are the original sources or material that have been created or collated to conduct a research project. They can be digital or non-digital. The response to a particular research question is based on the analysis of research data.</p>	Research Data Governance & Materials Handling Policy
NSW	University of Newcastle	<p>primary materials are physical objects acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which research data may be derived, including research material as defined in the Temperature Controlled Environments Policy. Examples of primary materials include ore, biological material, questionnaires and recordings;</p>	<p>research data is facts, observations, images, computer program results, recordings, measurements or experiences on which an argument, theory, test or hypothesis, or other research output is based. Data may be numerical, descriptive, visual, or tactile. It may be raw, cleaned or processed and may be held in any format or media (Australian National Data Service – What is research data, 2017);</p>		Research Data and Primary Materials Management Procedure
NSW	University of Sydney	<p>primary materials - means physical objects acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which research data may be derived. It may include raw physical materials such as ore, soil samples or biological material, or physical or digital objects such as artefacts, questionnaires, sound recordings or video. Depending on discipline, primary materials may be considered research data, and may be required to be retained if they are</p>	<p>It is not possible to apply a uniform definition of research data across all disciplines. Research data may be numerical, textual, audio-visual, digital or physical, depending on the discipline and the nature of the research.</p>	<p>Research Records means any document or other source of information compiled, recorded or stored in any form and which is maintained as evidence or information by an organisation or person, for use in their work.</p>	Research Data Management Policy

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
		required to validate the outcomes of research, and defend those outcomes against challenge.			
NSW	University of Technology, Sydney	<p>Primary materials are physical objects acquired through a process of scholarly investigation that may derive research data. Examples include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • raw physical materials such as rock samples • biological materials such as biospecimens, cell lines and related products (genetic material), or • physical artefacts such as film, photographs or recordings (not stored or available elsewhere). 	<p>Research data means data collected, generated or created during research, used to validate research findings and/or used to enable reproduction of the research. It can be digital, non-digital, observational, experimental, simulation, derived or reference material.</p>	<p>Research records means any documentation or information prepared, maintained or stored as evidence by the university or individuals for use in their work, and includes correspondence (hardcopy and electronic), grant application documentation, human or animal ethics protocols (applications, approvals and related documents), signed participant consent forms and information sheets for research participants, research data management plans, authorship agreements, technical reports, research reports (to project or funding board) and other items like these.</p>	<p>Research Policy</p>
NSW	Western Sydney University		<p>Any information collected, captured or created in digital or non-digital formats to support research projects at Western Sydney University. It includes all hard copy material generated in the course of research, together with all digital material on which research findings, interpretations and/or observations may rely. Research data may comprise any content or take any form, including numbers, symbols, text, images or sounds. Research data may also include information concerning how, when, where and with what methods research data were collected. Material constituting research data is commonly accepted as the evidence that validates research findings.</p>		<p>POLICY GLOSSARY</p>
NSW	University of Wollongong	<p>Physical objects that are collected or used for research, from which data may be obtained. For example, laboratory notebooks, interview recordings, biological specimens, and survey responses.</p>	<p>The data, records, files or other evidence, irrespective of their content or form (for example, in print, digital, physical or other forms), that comprise research observations, findings or outcomes, including primary materials and analysed data. Research data referred to in this policy relates to data generated in research projects and is to be distinguished from the information about research performance and statistical research data which is used for planning and budgeting purposes.</p>		<p>Research Data Management Guidelines</p>

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
QLD	Bond University	Physical objects acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which research data may be derived. It may include raw physical materials such as ore, soil samples or biological material, or physical or digital objects such as artefacts, questionnaires, sound recordings or video. Depending on discipline, primary materials may be considered research data, and may be required to be retained if RES 4.2.1 Research Data Management and Sharing Policy V1.1 Page 5 of 6 they are required to validate the outcomes of research and defend those outcomes against challenge. ¹	Data are facts, observations or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Data may be numerical, descriptive or visual. Data may be raw or analysed, experimental or observational. Data includes: laboratory notebooks; field notebooks; primary research data (including research data in hardcopy or in computer readable form); questionnaires; audiotapes; videotapes; models; photographs; films; test responses. Research collections may include slides; artefacts; specimens; samples. Provenance information about the data might also be included: the how, when, where it was collected and with what (for example, instrument). The software code used to generate, annotate or analyse the data may also be included. ² Research data and primary materials will also include evidence to support the formulation of the hypotheses and findings in areas such as text-based research. It also includes creative outputs, for example drafts of original literary and musical works, and musical performances, as recognised or defined by evaluative processes such as Excellence in Research for Australia (ERA).		Research Data Management and Sharing Policy
QLD	CQ University	Materials: physical objects acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which research data may be derived. It may include raw physical materials such as ore, soil samples or biological material, or physical or digital objects such as artefacts, questionnaires, sound recordings or video. Depending on discipline, materials may be considered research data, and may be required to be retained if they are required to validate the outcomes of research, and defend those outcomes against challenge. ¹	broadly refers to the 'evidence base' for the research, including working and final versions on which the research or creative work is based. This could include facts, observations or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Data may be numerical, descriptive or visual. Data may be raw or analysed, experimental or observational. Data includes laboratory notebooks, field notebooks, primary research data (including research data in hardcopy or in computer readable form), questionnaires, audiotapes, videotapes, models, photographs, films or test responses. Research collections may include slides, artefacts, specimens or samples. Provenance information about the data might also be included: the how, when, where it was collected and with what (for example, instrument). The software code used to generate, annotate or analyse the data may also be included. ² For creative works this could include images of visual artwork (e.g. sculpture, paintings, exhibitions), recordings of performances and musical works (e.g. rehearsals, live performances, digital output), and textual works (e.g. drafts/concept maps/manuscripts/novella/work of fiction/musical composition).		Research Data Management Policy and Procedure

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
QLD	Federation University of Australia	Print, digital or physical objects collected and/or used during scholarly activity and investigation from which research data may be obtained. It includes materials such as biological samples, mineral samples, survey questionnaires, measurements, recordings, computer results, and artefacts (including design).	<p>Data generated during research projects. Research data can include data in the form of facts, observations, images, samples, computer program results, recordings, measurements or experiences on which argument, test or hypotheses, or another research output is based. Data may be numerical, descriptive, visual or tactile. It may be raw, cleaned, or processed, and may be held in any format or media. It includes laboratory notebooks, as well as any other records, including computer code, that are necessary for the construction and evaluation of reported results of research, and the events and processes leading to those results.</p> <p>Research data is to be distinguished from the information about research performance and statistical data which is used by the University for planning and budgetary purposes and reported by the University to government agencies (for example and including the Higher Education Research Data Collection, HERDC, and Excellence in Research for Australia, ERA).</p>		Research Data Management Procedure
QLD	Griffith University		research data are defined as: factual records, which may take the form of numbers, symbols, text, images or sounds, used as primary sources for research, and that are commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings. This definition aims to be technology-neutral, in that it omits any reference to the media in which the records are made. The research community would be particular to the field of research. This allows for conventions in particular disciplines, as manifest in journal editorial policies for example, on what is regarded as data that need to be kept.		Retention Periods for Research Data and Primary Materials
QLD	James Cook University	Is print, digital or physical objects collected and/or used during scholarly activity and investigation from which research data may be obtained. It includes materials such as ore, biological material, questionnaires or recordings and also includes durable records derived from them (such as assays, test results, transcripts, and laboratory and field notes). Primary material may be research data or information.	Is any data that has been collected, generated or created (no authorship) during a research project. It may be raw, cleaned, or processed (via machine), and may be held in any format or media. May also be referred to as primary material.		Management of Data and Information in Research Procedure

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
QLD	Queensland University of Technology	means physical objects collected and/or used during research from which research data may be obtained. It includes, but is not limited to, materials such as biological samples, mineral samples, survey questionnaires, measurements, recordings, artwork and photographs.	means data in the form of facts, observations, images, computer program results, recordings, measurements or experiences on which an argument, theory, test or hypothesis, or other research output is based. It relates to data generated, collected, or used, during research projects, and in some cases may include the research output itself. Data may be numerical, descriptive, visual or tactile. It may be raw, cleaned or processed, and may be held in any format or media. Research data, in many disciplines, may by necessity include the software, algorithm, model and/or parameters, used to arrive at the research outcome, in addition to the raw data that the software, algorithm or model is applied to.		Management of research data and primary materials
QLD	University of Queensland	objects (physical or virtual) acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which Research Data may be derived.	includes all data created and/or generated by Researchers in the course of their research work, on which an argument, theory, test or hypothesis, or another research output is based, for which the University has a custodial responsibility under relevant agreements and the relevant archives/record keeping acts.		Research Data Management
QLD	University of Southern Queensland	Physical objects acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which Research Data may be derived. Includes, but is not limited to, ore, biological material, survey questionnaires, measurements, recordings, artefacts, texts, photographs, and computer results. In some instances, Primary materials may be considered research data, and may be required to be retained to validate the outcomes of research.	Research data relates to facts, observations, measurements or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Research Data may be numerical, descriptive, visual or tactile. It may be raw, or analysed, experimental or observational and may be held in any format or media. Research data (and primary materials) includes evidence supporting findings. For example, in the Creative Arts this may include early drafts and concept documents prior to the final output of the creative work.		Research Data
QLD	University of the Sunshine Coast	physical or virtual objects acquired or derived through a process of scholarly investigation from which research data may be derived. It includes but is not limited to: ore; biological materials; questionnaires or recordings.	any data collected during research that could be used to validate the research findings and/or facilitate the reproduction of the research. This includes data in all forms (e.g. electronic, lab notes, surveys, field notes, datasets, audio recordings, test results).		Research Data Management - Procedures
SA	Flinders University		means the primary and secondary data, records, files or other elements that form the basis of the main inferences, observations, findings, conclusions, outcomes or elements of a research project or publication, irrespective of the form in which it exists, e.g., in print, electronic, physical, multi-media or other forms.		Research Data Management - Procedures

State/Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
SA	Torrens University Australia	objects, physical and/or virtual, acquired through a process of research from which research data may be derived, examples include biological material, survey questionnaires, recordings and images.	the data, records, files or other evidence, irrespective of their content or form, that comprise research observations, findings or outcomes, including primary materials and analysed data. Research data referred to in this policy relates to data generated in research projects and excludes those derived as part of the University's operations.		Research Data Management Policy
SA	University of Adelaide	Physical objects acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which research data may be derived. It may include raw physical materials such as ore, soil samples or biological material, or physical or digital objects such as artefacts, questionnaires, sound recordings or video. Depending on discipline, primary materials may be considered research data, and may be required to be retained if they are required to validate the outcomes of research, and defend those outcomes against challenge. ²	Data are facts, observations or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Data may be numerical, descriptive or visual. Data may be raw or analysed, experimental or observational. Data includes: laboratory notebooks; field notebooks; primary research data (including research data in hardcopy or in computer readable form); questionnaires; audiotapes; videotapes; models; photographs; films; test responses. Research collections may include slides; artefacts; specimens; samples. Provenance information about the data might also be included: the how, when, where it was collected and with what (for example, instrument). The original software code used to generate, annotate or analyse the data is included. ⁴ Research data and primary materials will also include evidence to support the formulation of the hypotheses and findings in areas such as text-based research. It also includes creative outputs, for example drafts of original literary and musical works, and musical performances, as recognised or defined by evaluative processes such as Excellence in Research for Australia (ERA).		Research Data and Primary Materials Policy
SA	University of South Australia	includes, but is not limited to, ore, biological material, photographs, artwork, questionnaires or recordings acquired through undertaking research from which Research Data are derived.			Ownership and Retention of Data
TAS	University of Tasmania		Research data is defined as: i. all data which is created by researchers in the course of their work, and for which the University has a curatorial responsibility for at least the minimum duration required by the Code and relevant archives/record keeping acts, ii. third-party data which may have originated within the institution or come from elsewhere, iii. primary materials necessary to validate research findings, including data, materials, specimens, samples or information acquired through a process of scholarly investigation by the researcher in its raw, unanalysed state as part of their research and from which research data are derived. Research data includes facts, observations, measurements or experiences on which an argument,		Research Data Management Procedure

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
			theory or test is based. Research data may be numerical, descriptive or visual; raw or analysed, experimental or observational. Includes laboratory notebooks, field notebooks, primary research data, questionnaires, audiotapes, videotapes, models, photographs, films, test responses, primary materials (including, but is not limited to, ore, core samples, minerals and rocks; biological materials; the products of a process where the material is stable and can be stored for the requisite time; questionnaires; recordings; films; test responses; photographs; models; videotapes; audiotapes; or any other materials acquired through undertaking research) and any other records that are necessary for the reconstruction and evaluation of the reported results of research.		
VIC	Deakin University		All data that is created by researchers in the course of their work, and for which the University has a curatorial responsibility for the required retention periods, and third-party data that may have originated within the University or come from elsewhere. This excludes administrative and teaching data and research publications.		Research Data Management Procedure
VIC	La Trobe University	Data, materials, specimens, samples or information generated or collected by the researcher in its raw, unanalysed state as part of their research	Data or information collected, generated, created or observed which is used to validate research findings		Research Data Management Policy
VIC	Monash University		the data, records, files or other evidence, irrespective of their content or form (e.g. in print, digital, physical or other forms), that comprise a research project's observations, findings or outcomes, including primary materials and analysed data.		Research Data Management : Staff, Adjuncts and Visitors Procedures
VIC	RMIT University	Primary materials includes but is not limited to ore, core samples, minerals and rocks; biological materials; the products of a process where the material is stable and can be stored for the requisite time; questionnaires; recordings; films; test responses; photographs; models; videotapes; audiotapes; or any other materials acquired through undertaking research from which research data are derived	Research data are facts, observations or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Research data may be: - numerical, descriptive or visual, - durable records derived from primary materials such as assays, test results, transcripts, laboratory and field notes, visual diaries, journals, audio and visual recordings, oral history sound files, performance recordings, archival data and metadata, webistes, photographs and images, - raw or analysed, experimental or observational, - other documents or media containing information associated with the research process, - digital and non-digital.		Research Data Management Procedure
VIC	Swinburne University of Technology	Physical objects or raw electronic data, acquired through the process of scholarly investigation from which research data may be derived. It includes inorganic and biological	Records, files or other evidence, irrespective of their content or form (e.g. in print, digital, physical or other forms), that comprise research observations, findings or outcomes. This includes		Research Data Management : Guidelines &

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
		material, questionnaires or audio and visual recordings.	primary materials and analysed data.		Planning for Researchers
VIC	University of Melbourne		Research data means any information, facts or observations that have been collected, recorded or used during the research process for the purpose of substantiating research findings. Research data may exist in digital, analogue or combined forms and such data may be numerical, descriptive or visual, raw or processed, analysed or unanalysed, experimental, observational or machine generated. Examples of research data include: documents, spreadsheets, audio and video recordings, transcripts, databases, images, field notebooks, diaries, process journals, artworks, compositions, laboratory notebooks, algorithms, scripts, survey responses and questionnaires.		Research Data Management Policy (MPF1242)
VIC	Victoria University	Physical objects acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which Research Data may be derived. Includes, but is not limited to, ore, biological material, survey questionnaires, measurements, recordings, artefacts, texts, photographs, and computer results.	Facts, observations or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Data may be numerical, descriptive or visual. Data may be raw or analysed, experimental or observational. Data includes: laboratory notebooks; field notebooks; primary research data (including research data in hardcopy or in computer readable form); questionnaires; audiotapes; videotapes; models; photographs; films; test responses. Research collections may include slides; artefacts; specimens; samples. Provenance information about the data might also be included: the how, when, where it was collected and with what (for example, instrument). The software code used to generate, annotate or analyse the data may also be included.		Research Integrity - Research Data Management Procedure
WA	Curtin University	Primary materials includes but is not limited to ore, core samples, minerals and rocks; biological materials; the products of a process where the material is stable and can be stored for the requisite time; questionnaires; recordings; films; test responses; photographs; models; videotapes; audiotapes; or any other materials acquired through undertaking research from which research data are derived.	Research data are facts, observations or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Research data may be: numerical, descriptive or visual durable records derived from primary materials such as assays, test results, transcripts, and laboratory and field notes raw or analysed, experimental or observational other documents or media containing information associated with the research process.		Research Data and Primary Materials Policy

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
WA	Edith Cowan University		<p>Facts, observations or experiences on which an argument, theory or test is based. Data may be numerical, descriptive or visual. Data may be raw or analysed, experimental or observational. Data includes records, files and other evidence, irrespective of their content or form. Data may be digital, non-digital (in print, lab notebooks, field notebooks, questionnaires, audiotapes, videotapes, models, photographs, films, test responses) or primary materials (geological, biological, chemical, etc.). In the creative arts, data includes the creative artefacts of human expression that have emerged via text, visual arts, performing arts and music where both the expressive artefact and the process of creating that artefact are the objects of investigation. Data can be ephemeral and multifaceted and should therefore be thought of as the shifting and constantly re-evaluated set of emergent ideas that find embodiment in the final artwork. For this mode of research, a durable record of the response to the data should be maintained, for example, as a visual diary, recording or journal.</p>		Research Data Management Guidelines
WA	Murdoch University		<p>Research data include 'records, files or other evidence, irrespective of their content or form (e.g., in print, digital, physical or other forms), that comprise research observations, findings or outcomes, including primary materials and analysed data' (ANDS, 2017, p. 2). This includes all data created or collected during the course of original research activities and for which the University has a shared responsibility to store, maintain or otherwise curate. Research data may be numerical, descriptive, visual, or tactile. It may be raw or analysed, cleaned or processed, experimental or observational, confidential or publicly accessible, and may be held in any format or media. Examples include laboratory and field notebooks, machine data in hardcopy or computer readable form, databases, clinical data including clinical records, questionnaires, photographs, audio-visual materials, test responses, physical collections of slides, artefacts, manuscripts, specimens, samples, or other forms to be developed in the future.</p> <p>In the creative arts or other areas where the research component of a work may not be immediately apparent within a performance, exhibition or creative publication, a durable record of the work and or the response to the work should be retained as evidence of the research process. Examples may include an artist's statement, exhibition catalogues, critical reviews of a performance or publication, visual diaries, journals, drawings, photographs, manuscripts, musical</p>		Research Data Management Policy

State/ Territory	Organisation	Primary/Research Materials	Research Data	Other	Source
			<p>annotations 3D models or audio-visual recordings of the creative work outcomes, including primary materials and analysed data. It excludes organisational administrative data (such as finance, human resource, and student records), teaching related data (courseware and learning management) and research publications themselves. Although there may be overlaps, 'research data' is distinct from 'intellectual property' as outlined in the Murdoch University Intellectual Property Regulations which refers to research outputs that normally have commercial value.</p>		
WA	University of Notre Dame Australia	<p>Primary Materials means Objects (physical or virtual) acquired through a process of scholarly investigation from which Research Data may be derived.</p>	<p>Research Data means all data, inclusive of Primary Materials, created and/or generated by Researchers in the course of their research work, on which argument, theory, test or hypothesis, or another research output is based, and for which the University has a custodial responsibility under the relevant Agreements and the relevant archives/record keeping Acts.</p>		<p>Policy: Research Data Management</p>